

Factors Related To Medication Adherence among Persons with Hypertension in Nepal

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Abstract

Background: Hypertension is a crucial worldwide health concern and a fatal disease. Medication adherence is essential in managing blood pressure, decreasing the likelihood of stroke, reducing the risk of kidney disease, improving renal outcomes, lowering mortality rates, and minimizing healthcare costs. **Purpose:** This study aimed to examine perceived susceptibility, perceived severity, perceived benefit, perceived barrier, and self-efficacy among persons with hypertension and the relationship between them in Nepal. **Methods:** The descriptive correlation study was conducted with 212 hypertensive persons from the Outpatient Department of AMDA Hospital, Nepal. Data were collected using validated instruments between February 2023 to April 2023. The research instruments included the Medication Adherence Report Scale (MARS-5), the Health Belief for Hypertensive Patient Scale (HBHS), and the Medication Adherence Self Efficacy Scale Revised (MASES-R). Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and Spearman's rank correlation. **Results:** The results revealed that the overall medication adherence level in this study was non-adherent 72.64% (mean 20.12, SD 3.31, range 10-25). Perceived susceptibility ($r = 0.07$, $p = 0.32$) and perceived benefits ($r = 0.10$, $p = 0.13$) did not correlate with medication adherence. However, the perceived severity ($r = 0.16$, $p = 0.02$), perceived barrier ($r = 0.19$, $p = 0.01$), and self-efficacy ($r = 0.23$, $p = 0.00$) had a weak positive correlation with medication adherence. **Conclusions:** The study results highlight the importance of medication adherence and the factors associated with medication adherence in persons with hypertension. The findings can be applied to develop strategies to enhance medication adherence by considering factors such as the perceived severity of the disease, perceived barriers, and self-efficacy in patients with hypertension in Nepal.

Keywords: Health Belief Model, Hypertension, Medication Adherence, Nepal.

BACKGROUND

Hypertension (HT) is a significant worldwide health concern and a fatal disease (Benjamin et al., 2019). It affects over one billion people globally, and this is expected to increase continuously (Center for Disease Control and Prevention, 2021). According to the WHO World Profile 2023, HT affects significant populations worldwide, with the highest prevalence in China (256.7 million) and India (188.3 million), and lower numbers in Australia (4.8 million) and France (14.1 million). In Nepal, 3.9 million people have hypertension (World Health Organization, 2023). Hypertension was discovered to be the major risk factor for CVD, and death from its consequences (Wang et al., 2020). Since hypertension is associated with multiple complications, it is necessary to control blood pressure.

A review of the existing literature has revealed that medication adherence levels of patients with hypertension are below average. The medication adherence level in Ghana was found to be 59.5% (Abeasi et al., 2022) and in Iran, it was 33% (Oori et al., 2019). In Nepal, 72% of patients had low adherence to anti-hypertensive medication (Roka & Ghimire, 2020) while a recent systematic review and meta-analysis concluded that the pooled prevalence of non-adherence to anti-hypertensive medication was 49%. Non-adherence to hypertensive medication is a significant cause of uncontrolled HT (Abbas et al., 2020; Pan et al., 2021). Numerous studies have demonstrated the benefit of medication adherence in improving blood pressure control to decrease disease burden. For instance, higher antihypertensive medication adherence is related to blood pressure control (Bramley et al., 2006; Piercefield et al., 2017); lower risks of stroke (Xu et al., 2017); reduced risk of major cardiovascular disease events; and all-cause mortality (Ettehad et al., 2016). Non-adherence to medication has a substantial and multifaceted impact on the treatment of hypertension, developing the risk of cardiovascular events, poor renal outcomes, such as end-stage kidney disease, and all-cause mortality (Hamdidouche et al., 2017). Better medication adherence levels will lower the risk of cardiovascular events and all-cause mortality caused by hypertension (Liu et al., 2021).

Medication adherence is the extent to which a person's behavior, including medication-taking, corresponds with agreed recommendations from a healthcare provider (WHO, 2003). Medication adherence among people with hypertension is widely studied and identified factors include female gender (Tibebu et al., 2017); illiteracy (Berisa & Dedefo, 2018; Bhandari et al., 2015); income (Abeasi et al., 2022; Moss et al., 2021); duration of being on antihypertensive medication (Moss et al., 2021); co-morbid conditions (Asgedom et al., 2018; Roka & Ghimire, 2020); unavailability of medication (Abdisa et al., 2022; Moss et al., 2021); adverse effects of medication (Adidja et al., 2018; Yasmin Akhtar et al., 2022); forgetfulness (Adidja et al., 2018; Khadka et al., 2021); and social support (Olowookere & Akinboboye, 2015; Pan et al., 2021). The literature review revealed varying levels of medication adherence in Nepal, influenced by differences in measurement tools, populations, and settings. This study employs the MARS-5 questionnaire to fill gaps identified in earlier research by including nursing-related factors and replicating a study that previously excluded the Health Belief Model factors. This study aims to evaluate the impact of the Health Belief Model variables on medication adherence among hypertensive patients in Nepal, exploring factors such as perceived susceptibility, severity, benefits, barriers, and self-efficacy. The findings will enhance understanding of adherence levels and inform strategies to improve blood pressure management in this population.

Up to the present, there has been limited research based on the Health Belief Model. Furthermore, the associations between perceived susceptibility, perceived severity, perceived benefit, perceived barrier, self-efficacy, and medicine adherence have not been sufficiently reported. The results drawn from numerous studies are contradictory. However, based on the literature review, different studies from several countries had varying recruitment criteria, sample sizes, and sampling techniques. Furthermore, as those studies were conducted in various settings ranging from rural areas to tertiary hospitals, the findings cannot be generalized; thus, there is a need for more research in this area. Additionally, in Nepal, nurses have not deeply studied medication adherence in Nepalese patients using the Health Belief Model as a theoretical framework. As a nurse, educating and motivating patients to change their behavior is a main goal, so more research is needed to explore the relationship between medication adherence and the factors associated with it. Therefore, these five components were chosen as research variables for this study.

The conceptual framework used to guide this study was based on the Health Belief Model (HBM) developed by Rosenstock et al. (1988). The cornerstone of the HBM is the knowledge that an individual will make changes to their health behaviors if they believe they can prevent a negative

health condition, feel confident that they can successfully carry out the intended action, and have a positive expectation that their chosen behavior will lower the risk of the negative health condition (Hochbaum, 1958; Rosenstock, 1974). This study explores how the five HBM constructs perceived susceptibility, perceived severity, perceived benefits, perceived barriers, and self-efficacy affect medication adherence in hypertensive patients.

Based on the HBM (Hochbaum, 1958; Rosenstock, 1974), there are six constructs which include 1) perceived susceptibility, 2) perceived severity, 3) perceived benefits, 4) perceived barriers, 5) self-efficacy, and 6) cues to action (Glanz et al., 2008; Rosenstock, 1974). Perceived susceptibility refers to a perception of a person with hypertension about the likelihood of developing a hypertension-related health issue and complication. Perceived severity refers to the perceived impact of high blood pressure on the life of a person with hypertension. Perceived benefits refer to a belief of a person with hypertension about the value or usefulness of an adherent behavior in decreasing the risk of developing a disease. Perceived barriers refer to the obstacles that prevent a person with hypertension from taking their medications. Self-efficacy is defined as the conviction that one can successfully execute the behavior required to produce the outcomes (Bandura, 1999). In the present study, medication adherence, the extent to which patients follow healthcare recommendations, is analyzed as a dependent variable, with the HBM constructs serving as independent variables. The study examines how these factors influence adherence to prescribed medication. This study aimed to examine medication adherence, perceived susceptibility, perceived severity, perceived benefit, perceived barrier, and self-efficacy and their relationships, among persons with hypertension in Nepal.

METHODS

Study Design

A descriptive correlation study was employed in this study.

Sample/Participants

The study was conducted with hypertensive patients who attended AMDA (Association of Medical Doctors of Asia-Nepal) Hospital in Damak, Nepal. The inclusion criteria were: 1) 20 years of age or older, 2) having anti-hypertensive treatment for at least a 1-year duration with or without comorbid diseases, 3) voluntarily taking part in the research, 4) reading and writing the Nepali language, and 5) can communicate well. In the year (2079 BS as per the Nepali calendar), 6 to 7 hypertensive patients on average visited the AMDA hospital OPD. For this study, average patient visits consisted of five hypertensive cases per day; public holidays and Saturdays were excluded. The total population size was calculated from three months of hospital visits to the OPD. The sample size estimation was calculated based on Yamane's (1967) formula from a total population of 450 by setting a 95% confidence level and the margin of error as 0.05. Hence, the required sample size was 212.

Instruments

Four instruments were used for data collection. Except for the demographic data form, the other three instruments were used with permission from the developers. The list of the instruments are as follows:

1. The demographic questionnaire: This questionnaire was developed by the Principal Investigator (PI) to gather general demographic information covering gender, age, marital status, religion, level of education, employment status, duration of being diagnosed with hypertension, duration of taking antihypertensive drugs, number of pills, and comorbidity.

2. The Medication Adherence Report Scale (MARS-5): MARS-5 was developed by Chan et al. (2020) and consists of five statements, each describing a common non-adherent behavior. The respondents rate how often they behave as described by the various statements (I forget to take my medicines, I alter the dose of my medicines, I stop taking my medicines for a while, I decide to skip a dose, I take less than instructed) on a 5-point Likert scale (1-always, 2-often, 3-sometimes, 4-rarely, and 5-never). The first question focuses on unintentional nonadherence, while the other four questions reflect intentional non-adherence. MARS-5 total scores may range from 5 to 25, with higher scores indicating better medication adherence. In terms of total scores for the MARS-5, adherence was defined as scores of 23–25 while non-adherence included scores 5–22 (Norberg et al., 2022). The validity of the MARS-5 was 0.84 (Chan et al., 2020). For the Nepali version, the translation and back translation by Brislin (1970) was used. The reliability of the MARS-5 was examined among 30 participants, resulting in 0.82. The internal consistency of the MARS-5 was tested with 21 subjects from AMDA Hospital who met the inclusion criteria. The Cronbach alpha of MARS-5 was 0.82.
3. The Health Belief for Hypertensive Patients Scale (HBHS): The HBHS was developed by the PI modifying a questionnaire developed by Pinprapapan et al. (2013) and was used to measure the health beliefs of people with HTN in this study. The HBHS includes 25 items to measure four dimensions, including perceived susceptibility (7 items, items 1 to 7); perceived severity (5 items, items 8 to 12); perceived benefits (6 items, items 13 to 18); and perceived barriers (7 items, items 19 to 25). The participants respond to the items using a 4-point rating scale. The first 19 items with a positive meaning are coded, from 1 (strongly disagree) to 4 (strongly agree). Inversely, the rest of the items (7 items of perceived barriers) with a negative meaning are coded ranging from 1 (strongly agree) to 4 (strongly disagree). The whole score is acquired by summing the response values across all items and ranges from 25 to 100. The instrument was translated from Thai to English and English to Nepali using back translation by Brislin (1970). The measurement of the internal consistency of the HBHS was tested with 21 subjects who met the inclusion criteria from AMDA Hospital. The Cronbach alpha of the HBHS was 0.96. The CVI for the HBHS was analyzed by a panel of six experts, and it was 0.93. A CVI of more than 0.8 was acceptable (Burns, 2017). In this study, the four variables interpretation scores were classified into three categories: 0-10 (Low), 11-20 (Moderate), and 21-28 (High) for perceived susceptibility. Perceived severity ranges from 0 to 7 (low), 8 to 15 (moderate), and 16 to 20 (high). Interpretation scores for Perceived benefit were 0-8 (Low), 9-16 (Moderate), and 17-24 (High) and for Perceived barriers, were 0-10 (Low), 11-20 (Moderate), and 21-28 (High).
4. Medication Adherence Self-Efficacy Scale-Revised (MASES-R): The MASES-R, developed by Fernandez et al. (2008), involves 13 items with the first 12 items asking about the patient's confidence to adhere to antihypertensive medication in specific situations while the last item asks about their confidence to make taking medication a daily routine. For the Nepali version, the translation and back translation by Brislin (34) was used. The measurement of the internal consistency of the MASES-R was tested with 21 subjects from AMDA Hospital who met the inclusion criteria. The internal consistency reliability of the MASES-R was 0.97. An example question is: "How confident are you that you can take your antihypertensive medications when you feel well?" The participants rated the items using a 4-point rating scale: 1 (not at all sure); 2 (a little sure); 3 (fairly sure); and 4 (extremely sure). An overall score was achieved by obtaining an average across responses to all items. The total score was 52, and possible scores included 13-52. Higher scores meant higher levels of self-efficacy.

Data Collection

Data was collected from Feb 2023 to April 2023. The principal investigator prepared packages that included an information sheet, a consent form, and four questionnaires. Data was collected from hypertension patients who met the inclusion criteria while they were at the AMDA Hospital's OPD waiting area from Sunday to Friday of the three-month research period.

Participants completed questionnaires before their physician appointments, with the researcher explaining the study's purpose and ensuring voluntary participation and confidentiality.

After obtaining consent, the researcher provided four sets of questionnaires in Nepali and assisted participants with any queries. Participants were informed that the process would take 20 to 30 minutes; then, they returned their complete questionnaires to a designated box in the waiting area. Researchers collected the data until the desired sample was achieved.

Data Analysis

Data was analyzed using the SPSS statistical software package. Both descriptive and inferential statistics were used. For this study, the significance alpha was set at the level of 0.05. Demographic data was analyzed by using frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation. The relationship between medication adherence and factors associated with medication adherence behaviors was analyzed by Spearman rank order correlation. The Kolmogorov-Smirnov (KS) test was used to assess normality, and the distribution was found to be non-normal.

Ethical Considerations

This study was conducted with the approval of the Research Ethics Committee of the Nursing Faculty, Chiang Mai University (Approval No 2023-EXP100) and the Nepal Health and Research Council (Ref. No.1181). Following this approval, the Medical Superintendent of AMDA Hospital, who is the hospital director, gave the PI permission and visibility to collect the required sample. Each participant signed the consent form after receiving information regarding the objectives, methods, instruments, confidentiality management, and their right to withdraw from the study.

RESULTS

Demographic Data of the Participants

As shown in Table 1, the participants were composed of 108 men (50.94%) and 104 women (49.06%). The ages of the participants ranged from < 35 to > 75 years. The majority of the participants were married, accounting for 94.34%. Most of the participants were Hindu (82.55%), and nearly half had completed elementary school to middle school (45.28%) while 35.38% had completed the SLC (School Leaving Certificate).

In terms of tertiary study, 16.51% had completed a bachelor's degree. Regarding employment, 40.56% were self-employed, 32.08% were unemployed and 7.07% were retired. For most participants, average duration of hypertension was 1 to 10 years (78.77%), and average HTN medication duration was 1 to 10 years (79.25%).

The majority of participants took 1 to 3 pills per day (84.90%). The participants had a range of comorbid conditions, including diabetes, kidney disease, heart disease, thyroid disorder, high cholesterol, COPD, gout, and prostate enlargement.

Table 1: Frequency and Percentage of Demographic Characteristics of the Participants (n = 212)

Demographic Characteristics	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Males	108	50.94
Females	104	49.06
Age (years old) (mean = 54.90, SD = 11.09, range 34-88)		
< 35 years old	1	0.50
36-45 years old	52	24.52
46-55 years old	66	31.13
56-65 years old	55	25.94
66-75 years old	28	13.20
> 75 years old	10	4.71
Marital Status		
Single	10	4.72
Married	200	94.34
Divorced	2	0.94
Religion		
Hindu	175	82.55
Buddhist	21	9.91
Muslim	2	0.94
Christian	14	6.60
Demographic Characteristics	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Education Level		
Below SLC	96	45.28
SLC	75	35.38
Bachelor Degree	35	16.51
Master's Degree	6	2.83
PHD	0	0.00
Employment Status		
Unemployed	68	32.08
Self-employed	86	40.56
Retired	15	7.08
Other	43	20.28
Hypertension Duration in Years		
1-10	167	78.77
11-20	39	18.40
21-30	5	2.36
Above 30	1	0.47
Hypertension Medication Duration		
1-10	168	79.25
11-20	38	17.92
21-30	5	2.36
Above 30	1	0.47
Pills per day		
1-3	180	84.90
4-6	29	13.68
Above 7	3	1.42
Demographic Characteristics	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Comorbid Conditions		
Diabetes	65	30.66
Kidney Disease	15	7.08
Heart Disease	15	7.08
Thyroid Disorder	8	3.77
High Cholesterol	3	1.42
COPD	4	1.88
Gaut	1	0.47
Prostate Enlargement	1	0.47
No Comorbidity	100	47.17

Medication Adherence among Persons with Hypertension

Among the 212 participants, 154 (72.6%) were identified as non-adherent, while 58 (27.3%) were adherent. The MARS-5 scores varied between 10 and 25, with a mean score of 20.12, indicating non-adherence, and a standard deviation of 3.31.

Table 2: Medication Adherence Level (Adherence and Non-adherence Score) (n = 212)

Adherence Score (mean = 20.12, SD = 3.31, range 10-25)		
	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Non-adherence	154	72.64
Adherence	58	27.36
Total	212	100.00

The Perceived Susceptibility, Perceived Severity, Perceived Benefits, Perceived Barriers, and Self-efficacy Among Persons with Hypertension

The overall score of perceived susceptibility was at a high level, ranging from 7 to 28 with a mean of 23.49 (SD = 4.98). Secondly, the perceived severity score of participants ranged from 5 to 20 with a mean of 16.80 (SD = 3.30) which was at a moderate level. Thirdly, the perceived benefits score of participants ranged from 6 to 24 with a mean of 19.38 (SD = 4.18), which was at a high level. The overall score for perceived barriers ranged from 7 to 28 with a mean of 16.50 (SD = 6.19) which was at a moderate level. The overall score for self-efficacy ranged from 21 to 52 with a mean of 37.65 (SD = 8.23) which was at a high level.

Table 4: The Perceived Susceptibility, Perceived Severity, Perceived Benefits, Perceived Barriers, and Self-efficacy Among Persons with Hypertension (n = 212)

Factors Related to Medication Adherence	Possible score	Actual score	Mean	SD	Level
Perceived Susceptibility	7-28	7-28	23.49	4.98	High
Perceived Severity	5-20	5-20	16.80	3.30	Moderate
Perceived Benefits	6-24	6-24	19.38	4.18	High
Perceived Barriers	7-28	7-28	16.50	6.19	Moderate
Self-efficacy	13-52	21-52	37.65	8.23	Moderate

Relationship between Medication Adherence and Perceived Susceptibility, Perceived Severity, Perceived Benefits, Perceived Barriers and Self-efficacy

Table 3: Relationship Between Medication Adherence and Perceived Susceptibility, Perceived Severity, Perceived Benefits, Perceived Barriers, and Self-efficacy (n = 212)

Variables	Medication Adherence	
	Correlation coefficient (r)	p-value
Perceived Susceptibility	0.07	0.32
Perceived Severity	0.16	0.02
Perceived Benefits	0.10	0.13
Perceived Barriers	0.19	0.01**
Self-efficacy	0.23	0.00**

Note. **Spearman's rank order correlation test, $p < .01$; *Spearman's rank order correlation test, $p < .05$.

The analysis revealed no significant relationship between perceived susceptibility and medication adherence ($r = 0.07, p = 0.32$). Perceived severity showed a weak positive correlation with adherence ($r = 0.16, p = 0.02$). There was no significant correlation between perceived benefits and medication adherence ($r = 0.10, p = 0.13$). Perceived barriers had a weak positive correlation with

adherence ($r = 0.19$, $p = 0.01$), while self-efficacy exhibited a weak positive relationship with medication adherence ($r = 0.23$, $p = 0.00$).

DISCUSSION

Summary of the findings

Medication adherence among patients with hypertension in this study was found to be non-adherent (72.60 %). The reason for this low medication adherence could be due to a comorbid condition (Abdisa et al., 2022; Roka & Ghimire, 2019). This finding was consistent with previous studies (Abeasi et al., 2022; Roka & Ghimire, 2019) which may be a result of the comparable contexts, as all studies were conducted in underdeveloped nations, including one in Africa and one in Iran, which both exhibit similarities to Nepal. As a small middle-income country, Nepal struggles with medication adherence due to overburdened healthcare providers, limited access to facilities, and inadequate counseling. To improve services for its diverse population, the healthcare system needs to expand its qualified and competent workforce (Shah et al., 2021). Low medication adherence can be attributed to socioeconomic issues, demographic factors, irregular follow-up schedules, challenges in obtaining prescription drugs, forgetfulness, and a lack of perceived seriousness regarding missed doses (Chaudhary et al., 2024). The findings highlight the need for better medication adherence among Nepalese individuals with hypertension. The variation in adherence rates can be attributed to differences in how adherence was measured and the characteristics of the study populations. While some previous studies employed the MMAS-4 or self-developed questionnaires, this study utilized the MARS-5 questionnaire. In summary, the results of this study indicated the necessity of awareness and health education among persons with hypertension in Nepal. Healthcare providers need to educate and provide enough information to patients about medication adherence.

In this study, there was no correlation between medication adherence and perceived susceptibility ($r = 0.07$, $P = 0.32$). The results were similar to an earlier research study conducted in Tanzania which revealed that perceived susceptibility had a weak association with medication adherence ($r = 0.141$, $p < 0.05$) (Joho, 2012). Hypertension awareness and effort in blood pressure management were low in a previous study in Nepal (Shrestha et al., 2021). The government is attempting to increase public awareness about health (GON, 2014), but knowledge levels remain insufficient. Despite initiatives to promote awareness, most funding in Nepal relies on out-of-pocket expenditures, leaving participants financially burdened when purchasing medications, even though they understand the potential consequences (Baral & Koirala, 2021). This study differs from previous research as most participants were from the Hindu community, which influenced their beliefs about disease and susceptibility. Additionally, variations in medication assessment tools across studies may contribute to these differences.

Perceived severity was found to have a weak positive relationship with medication adherence ($r = 0.16$, $p = 0.02$) which was in line with a study conducted in China ($r = 0.104$, $p < 0.05$) (Joho, 2012). However, the finding was also inconsistent with another previous study in China.

This current study did not find any significant relationship between perceived benefit and medication adherence ($r = 0.10$, $p = 0.13$). The study participants lacked higher education, which may have affected their perceptions and contributed to non-adherence. One previous finding has shown that perceived benefit had a low positive relationship with medication adherence ($r = 0.27$; $P = 0.001$) (Joho, 2012). These inconsistent results could have come from the instrument used, the sample, the religious beliefs, or the health care cost facility of individual countries.

Perceived barriers had a weak positive correlation with medication adherence ($r = 0.19$, $p = 0.01$). When a person with hypertension encounters barriers when taking their prescribed medication,

their adherence will be disrupted. Consequently, those obstacles must be addressed to promote good adherence to the medication for hypertension. Moreover, prior research has indicated that a perceived barrier was the most substantial factor influencing medication nonadherence. Out-of-pocket healthcare expenditure is also a cause of non-adherence. The majority of participants in this study were unemployed, and the cost of medication needed to be managed by participants, which greatly affected adherence. The doctor-to-patient ratio is another challenge for Nepal. Currently, there is one doctor for every 850 people in the Kathmandu Valley, which surpasses the WHO's recommendation of 1 per 1000. However, in remote districts, this ratio drops significantly to 1 per 150,000 (Karki et al., 2024). These large disparities in doctor-to-patient ratios have impacted appointments and prolonged wait times, causing patients to cancel their follow-up appointments. In addition, a result in China concluded that a lower level of perceived barriers was associated with better antihypertensive medication adherence (Yue et al., 2015). This discrepancy might be due to Nepal's socio-economic status as an underdeveloped country in which communities cannot afford the cost of drugs and healthcare facilities. Those getting medicines free of cost had higher adherence than those who paid by themselves. The cost of medicine has greatly affected adherence to hypertensive medication which can explain the reason for non-adherence (Roka & Ghimire, 2019).

Self-efficacy had a weak positive relationship with medication adherence ($r = 0.23$, $p = 0.00$), a statement which is supported by Shen et al. (2020) who found that self-efficacy was an important mediating variable affecting medication adherence in hypertensive patients. A recent study found a strong positive correlation between self-efficacy and medication adherence ($r = 0.781$, $r = 0.591$) (Lestari & Anisa, 2022; Shen et al., 2020). This finding aligns with numerous previous studies worldwide, despite variations in research design or methods of measuring self-efficacy. Studies conducted in China and Indonesia have concluded that patients who had a higher level of self-efficacy had better adherence (Lestari & Anisa, 2022; Shen et al., 2020). However, the level of medication was found to be low in the present study. An earlier investigation has shown that lower levels of interaction with healthcare providers affect patients' self-efficacy (Khairy et al., 2021). Nepal's healthcare worker shortage restricts patient counseling time, emphasizing the need for targeted training sessions on hypertension management and control.

Limitations

This study has some limitations. Firstly, the data for this study comes from only one hospital in Koshi Province, Eastern Nepal. Therefore, the result may not be generalizable to persons with hypertension in different contexts due to the small geographic scope. Additionally, participants in this study were able to take medication independently. Thus, findings may be limited regarding those who are less independent in taking medication.

Implications for Nursing Practice

The findings of this research present basic information for nursing practice and research regarding the current situation on medication adherence and factors related to medication adherence in Nepal. First, nurses should educate patients with hypertension about the importance of taking their medications and the consequences of non-adherence. Additionally, nurses can use this study to increase perceived susceptibility, decrease perceived barriers, and improve self-efficacy for better control of blood pressure among persons with hypertension in Nepal. Healthcare providers, such as nurses, need to raise awareness about medication adherence. This study's findings can be used to raise awareness about low medication adherence and improving adherence in hypertensive patients. These findings can be applied to develop strategies to enhance medication adherence by considering factors such as the perceived severity of the disease, perceived barriers, and self-efficacy in patients with hypertension in Nepal. Furthermore, an intervention and predictive study is recommended for

the perceived severity of the disease, perceived barriers, and self-efficacy in patients with hypertension in Nepal.

CONCLUSION

This study reported that medication adherence levels among persons with hypertension are low in Nepal, highlighting the importance of adherence in hypertensive patients. This finding emphasizes the role of nurses to increase perceived susceptibility, decrease perceived barriers, and improve self-efficacy to better control blood pressure among persons with hypertension in Nepal. Healthcare providers, such as nurses, need to raise awareness about medication adherence.

Declaration of Conflicting Interest

All authors declared no potential conflict of interest in the study.

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Authors' Contributions

All authors contributed substantially to the conception and design, acquisition of data, data analysis, and interpretation of data. In addition, all drafted the manuscript or revised it critically for important intellectual content and provided approval of the final version.

Data Availability

The dataset generated and analyzed during the current study is available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Declaration of Use of AI in Academic Writing

The author used Quillbot and Grammarly in the writing process to improve readability and remove grammatical errors.

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